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“THE GRAVES IN THE SKY”

My ears tingle, the hairs on my body rising in gooseflesh
Their soft caresses, posing me frigid—breathless
I paint the sky soaked in deep fear

My throat closes, hands steady, scribbling their tears
I’ve painted the dead since my eyes have opened,
Each soul a shade the sky has broken
Veils in the vast swim with fervent

Yearning for hues that hold them at last
A stroke of colour makes them lose their head
They weave through veils in violet thread
Echoes of life they once had bled

Blossom where memories silently tread
The welkin glitters with twinkling lights
Each a welcome, a gleam of the night
Shadows graze my outstretched hands

Each curious where the soul may stand
The sun shall dip beyond the horizon
A symbol of hope and memory of all
Say hello to the dead of the night
They litter the heavens in colours in tow